

Didactical Determinants In Mechanical Design Learning With Using Modeling And Simulation Tool

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 22,2025</p> <p>Accepted: April 25 ,2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Didactical Determinants, Modeling Tools, Mechanical Design Learning</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15283196</p>	<p><i>This paper presents the results of a study on use of modeling and simulation tools in mechanical design learning. Indeed, the introduction of modeling and simulation tools in teaching-learning activities has opened up new opportunities for learning mechanical design. Modeling tools are used for the development of virtual models intended for sizing and optimisation, and/or validating the behaviour and performance of a system, component, or process. However, their use in the learning activities of mechanical design gives rise sometimes to many problems to student. These problems are often related to the educational use of these tools, the ergonomics of their interfaces, and their interaction with student. This research presents the main results of a quantitative study on the learning of mechanical design. A survey using a questionnaire was conducted among 67 first-year tertiary students. The results of the study identified didactical determinants that promote the efficiency of student mechanical design learning using modelling and simulation tools.</i></p>

Introduction

Efficiency of product design and optimisation remains an ongoing challenge for industrial production units. To meet the challenge, they use modelling tools to support the process of creating and manufacturing products. In the field of mechanical design, industrial production units use modelling and simulation tools in mechanical design work. Faced with the issue of inadequate training and employment within workplaces, technological education institutions introduce these same modelling and simulation tools into the mechanical design teaching-learning.

The introduction of software or modelling tools in teaching-learning activities in industrial science and technology opens up new opportunities for mechanical design teaching-learning in technological education institutions (Bonnardel & Didier, 2020; Didier, 2017). Indeed, the use of an artifact, such as the modelling and simulation tool in teaching-learning activities, presupposes the consideration and modification of instrumental and ergonomic genesis, a modification of teaching practices, and conceptualisation of these practices (Pellerin, 2015). Learning mechanical design by means of a modeling tool can be understood as the appropriation considered as the effective and concrete implementation of a tool by individuals within an organization (Brillet, et al., 2010). This study focuses on the use of modeling tools in learning mechanical design. With the new environment of modeling tools and their potential, the teacher of the discipline of mechanical design will have to question didactical determinants that promote learning. What difficulties do modelling and simulation tools pose to students in the process of learning mechanical design? How can teachers and students be helped to understand modelling and simulation tools in this teaching-learning process? These questions justify the relevance of conducting this research which seeks to contribute to the improvement of the quality of learning of mechanical design in higher technological education institutions.

This article aims to analyze the joint activity of teachers and students when using modeling tools in mechanical design by identifying the didactic determinants likely to favour the learning process of students.

Mechanical Design and Modelling Tools

The design of technical systems is defined by the sum of operations that allows a person to explain an idea by giving it a tangible or virtual reality (Bécheau & Bourgeois, 2013). It is a complex process of predicting the materiality of an object that does not yet exist, but exists only in the mind of those who are able to conceive it (Lebahar, 2008). In this regard, it consists of giving a set of propositions to describe a product (shape, dimension, means of manufacturing) and estimate its specifications. From an operational point of view, mechanical design reveals four categories of design, namely: *routine design*, *redesign*, *innovative design*, and *creative design*. All of these categories share a common thread in design activities: knowing and understanding the needs of the customer; defining the problem to address the identified needs; conceptualising the solution; performing the analysis; optimising the proposed solution; verifying the design obtained; and determining whether it meets the initial needs of the customer (Gericke & Blessing, 2012; Goldschmidt, 2014).

The following three important steps (Figure 1) are usually found in the various existing methodologies: (1) a simple definition of the problem to satisfy the requirements; (2) a conceptual definition which sets up the functional structure, the physical principles, and proposes a concept; and (3) a more detailed definition, which provides a complete description of the design.

Figure 1. Product design process

At certain stages, the resort to modelling could be systematic. This reflection on mechanical design and modelling focuses on the use of modelling and simulation tools in the teaching-learning activities of mechanical design at tertiary institutions.

Problem

Use modelling and simulation tools in learning mechanical design in industrial sciences and technologies has produced qualitative transformations in learning practices (Abouelala et al., 2015). Thus, students are confronted with changes and problems related to the educational use of these tools, the ergonomics of their interfaces, and or their interaction with modelling tool. In other words, it becomes essential to question mechanical design learning by students, with modelling and simulation tools. Therefore, teachers need to be interested in the didactical determinants that promote student learning. In this regard, how do students learn mechanical design with modeling tools? If not, what are didactical determinants likely to improve student learning?

Theoretical Framework

To have a better understanding of the phenomenon, the present study is based on an approach that articulates three theoretical concepts. First of all, it presents the instrumental approach developed by Rabardel (1995), which relies on the importance of instrumental mediation. Then, the Engeström model on the "basic structure of an activity" which takes into account the social or collective dimension of the activities as well as the media coverage of the actions with the tools mobilised in the observed contexts. Finally, the ergonomic evaluation of the software interface which aims to evaluate the degree of user-friendliness and ease of access with the different menus of the CAD software.

Instrumental Approach

Today, the "interactionist" and "integrative" paradigm emphasises the articulation of several types of variables concerning the teacher, the student, and the situation (actors and learning environment) to understand the teaching practice (Héroul, 2019; Altet, 2019). This study fits into this paradigm. This research finds its theoretical basis in the instrumental approach developed by Rabardel (1995). This approach is based on the importance of instrumental mediation and distinguishes between an artifact and an instrument. The passage from the artifact to the instrument refers to a process of instrumental genesis that, according to Rabardel (1995), through usage, marks the gradual evolution of the use of the artefact.

Modeling of interactions between student and modeling tool (artefact)

This research refers to the theory of activity that deals with human activity, which is considered as a socially situated activity, such as that related to work or learning. Engeström (1987) developed a systemic model taking into account the socio-institutional infrastructure of the activity (elements of the community, work rules and organization). It places the individual at the heart of a system of activity made up of six interdependent poles (subject, tool, rules, division of labor, community and object). We refer to Engeström's systemic model to model the learning activity of mechanical design using a CAD software modeling tool (Figure 2) to answer the many questions that arise to improve efficiency of learning.

Figure 2. Schematisation of the subject/CAD software interaction according to the activity theory due to Engeström

This model expresses the relationship between the subject (student) and the object of the activity. The *object* is the transformation of the environment that is targeted by the activity (task to be accomplished, objective to achieve). Here, it is the realisation of a digital model of a technical system. The *tools or artifact* include the material or symbolic tools that mediate the activity (software or tools for modelling and simulation). The *community* refers to the subjects (or subgroups) that share the same object, such as industrialists, other universities and institutes, designers, developers, and users of CAD software. The *division of labour* includes both the horizontal distribution of actions between subjects and members of the community, and the vertical hierarchy of powers and statutes, such as the pedagogical leaders of the university, departments, and teachers. Finally, the *rules* denote the implicit and explicit norms, conventions, and habits that maintain and regulate actions and interactions within the system.

Ergonomic Evaluation of the Software

The ergonomics of the software interface is a quality factor for interactive systems. To approach the ergonomic evaluation of a software is to pose the problem of its *usability* (ISO 9241-11, 1998), its *usefulness*, and its *acceptability*.

These three dimensions were explored by Tricot et al., (2003) in the evaluation of Computer Environments for Human Learning. Figure 4 presents the criteria of the dimensions taken into account in the evaluation of a Human Learning Computing Environment (EIAH).

Figure 3. Dimensions of software evaluation

Research Objectives

In short, this research endeavours to improve the quality of learning process of mechanical design in higher education institutions. More specifically, he proposes to first describe the learning context of mechanical design with modeling tool, then it endeavours to explore the didactic determinants likely to influence the effectiveness

of pupil learning. This is achieved through a joint activity in relation to the use of a modeling and simulation tool in a global context of the teaching-learning activity of mechanical design.

Methodology

The theoretical framework presented above introduced an approach to describe the global context of mechanical design teaching-learning. This allowed us to establish a more precise methodology to achieve the objectives stated above. This is described in more detail below.

Methodological Protocol

The methodological protocol (figure 5) is divided into four stages. As a first step, an interview questionnaire is administered to the teacher about the observed teaching session. It aims to clarify the didactic intentions of the professor in relation to his professional uses and the institutional context of intervention. Then, an observation grid is used about the observed teaching session. It seeks to give an account of the progress of the session, thus facilitating the possible analyzes in order to check the degree of coherence between the didactic approaches proposed and their effective implementation. Thirdly, a post-session interview with the teacher made it possible to review certain elements of the session, with the intention to define more precisely how the teacher adopts and adapts the modeling tool. Finally, a test on the realization of a digital model is administered to students after the teaching-learning session. After the test, a questionnaire is administered to the students. It makes it possible to specify the performance of the student in his interactions with the modeling tool and to evaluate his satisfaction on use of modeling tool in order to identify the usability problems posed by the interface. It also makes it possible to identify didactical determinants likely to influence effectiveness of the learning.

Figure 4. Methodological protocol

Data Gathering

The data were obtained from a survey conducted among 67 first-year students enrolled at the University Diploma of Technology (DUT) in Science and Industrial Techniques from Higher Normal School of Technical Education in Rabat (ENSET, Morocco).

The purpose of conducting the survey was to collect data to identify didactic determinants that could influence effectiveness of mechanical design learning process.

The questionnaire employed consisted of 31 items divided into four categories: student profile; software ergonomics; pedagogy of the software; and the interaction of the student with the modelling tool. The student questionnaire was built on a Likert scale with four response modes. The pre-test stage allowed for adjustments to be made to the questionnaire where necessary (AERA et al., 2014). The validation of the internal structure of the questionnaire and the reliability of the scale was ensured respectively by an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and a Cronbach alpha coefficient. A statistical analysis was then carried out on the independent variables and the dependent variable in order to test their interconnection. The quantitative data (questionnaire results) were analysed using Sphinx software, and the relationships between the variables were examined using the Khi^2 dependence test.

Measuring Variables

The dependent variable Y, representing "success in producing digital model of mechanical system?" The independent variables are linked to four factors composed of several criteria. The first factor relates to the student profile; the second to software ergonomics; the third to the pedagogy of the software; and finally, the fourth to the interaction of the student with the modelling and simulation tool when learning.

Figure 6 below presents criteria that can influence the success in realization digital model of the technical system.

Figure 5. Didactic determinants influencing effectiveness of learning mechanical design with CAD software

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to identify factors that may influence the effectiveness of students’ learning of the CAD software, which is represented by the dependent variable Y, we conducted a series of crosses. The χ^2 test made it possible to verify the degree of dependence between the variables. The main results are presented below.

Table 1. Significant dependence between profile factor and learning efficiency

Variable	χ^2	Df	(1-p)%	Statistical significance
Genre	0.30	2	13.74	Not statistically significant
Prereq_DesignModel	11.90	6	93.58	Little statistically significant
Prereq_DesignProcess	1.90	2	61.25	Not statistically significant
Prereq_Computer	3.20	2	79.86	Not statistically significant

Table 2. Significant dependence between Software ergonomics factor and learning efficiency

Variable	χ^2	Df	(1-p)%	Statistical significance
Suit_ObjContent	15.52	4	99.63	Very statistically significant
Suit_SceObjContent	4.63	4	67.31	Not statistically significant
Clarity	56	2	99.99	Very statistically significant
Discriminability	8.88	6	81.95	Not statistically significant
Concision	4.43	6	38.17	Not statistically significant
Consistency	5.80	6	55.42	Not statistically significant
Detectability	23.21	6	99.93	Very statistically significant
Readability	5.69	6	54.11	Not statistically significant
Comprehensibility	5.09	6	46.77	Not statistically significant
AdeqStudExpecta	20.66	4	99.96	Very statistically significant
InvestLearning	9.96	6	87.35	Little statistically significant

	Content								
Suit_ObjContent									1,00
Clarity	0,55								1,00
Detectability	0,50	0,61							1,00
AdeqStudExpecta	0,30	0,20	0,26						1,00
MotivStudent	0,28	0,50	0,48	0,45					1,00
SeqContent	0,22	0,12	0,14	0,15	0,19				1,00
AntiReturnActions	0,29	0,28	0,32	0,19	0,34	0,21			1,00
EasyStorSoftware	0,19	0,29	0,17	0,15	0,49	0,26	0,26		1,00
DIGITALMODEL	0,34	0,28	0,32	0,27	0,43	0,35	0,34	0,29	1,00

The values in Table 6 above depict the correlation coefficients between the criteria. An examination of the degree of correlation between the effectiveness of learning and each of the independent variables indicates that this correlation is both positive and significant, suggesting that these variables account for much of the variance in effectiveness of learning. The independent variables are also correlated to each other: the relevance of the objective to the content is better perceived if the content is clearly displayed and the student can easily locate the information present on the interface. The clarity of the content, the ease of localisation of the interface, the ease of memorisation, and the response to the expectations of the interface encourage the student to use the software. However, the degree of correlation observed is low ($r < 0.30$) in most cases. The Cronbach alpha coefficient (0.80) is also high. This value proves that the homogeneity and internal consistency of the eight criteria are satisfactory to understand the effectiveness of learning.

Figure 7: Factorial plan

The examination of the factorial plan (Figure 7) makes it possible to visualise the correlations between the variables. These are all located on the same side of the axis and therefore all contribute to the effectiveness of learning.

The factorial plan also shows that the 8 items explain 52% of the variance of the "learning effectiveness" variable. There is every reason to believe that the effectiveness of learning depends not only on the ergonomics, pedagogy, and interaction of the software, but also on the involvement and support of other members of the organising institution (e.g., director, professional non-teaching or support staff, and parents) to students.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of this paper was to explore the factors that promote the efficiency of mechanical design student's learning through the use of modelling and simulation tools. In the light of the existing literature on the

effectiveness of learning, and based on the empirical evidence available to us, we were able to develop a theoretical framework to understand the context within which the success of students' learning of mechanical design by using tool modelling could be determined, at least in part. The analysis is based on the hypothesis of student performance in interaction with a modelling and simulation tool (software) under the influence of four factors: *the student's profile*; *the software ergonomics*; *the software pedagogy*; and *the student's interaction with the modelling and simulation tool during learning*.

Overall, the effectiveness of learning is significantly associated with software ergonomics, pedagogy of the software, and the student's interaction with the modelling and simulation tool. However, ergonomics and pedagogy are the most important factors in explaining the effectiveness of student learning. A strong perception of the usefulness of the tools, the awareness of their usability and their acceptability are triggers that motivate the students. Thus, the joining of these three variables reinforces the ergonomics of the software. The perception of the ease of memorisation thus contributes to the effectiveness of learning by means of the modelling tool in the context of interacting with the software.

The results from the pedagogy of the software would constitute the Gordian knot of the use of modelling and simulation tools in the teaching-learning situations of mechanical design. Thence, the teacher should adopt an attitude of facilitation and mediation with students. Precisely, he/she should pay attention to the sequencing of the content, to the adequacy of the terms and notation between the software and the theoretical course, to the anti-return actions of the software, and to the presentation and the relevance of the proposed activities.

In terms of the pedagogical consequences, the teacher must always ensure mastery of the prerequisites, and if necessary, proceed with their activation while implementing remediation activities that would fill the gap. Motivation is one of the driving forces of functional didactics; the teacher must always be cognisant of the usefulness, usability, and acceptability of the tools that remain the levers of motivation.

To foster interaction with the software, the teacher will have to try to create a better perception of the ease of memorisation in order to enhance the effectiveness of learning. The ease of memorisation allows the student, after a more or less long period of non-use, to perform his/her tasks without having to relearn the operation of the modelling tool. All the factors mentioned must be seen as a bouquet, where the isolation of one would not be effective.

Notwithstanding the results we have achieved, there is reason to question the causality between the parameters and to proceed to broaden the field of study. The latter will allow a variety of targets and there for triangulation of approaches by focus in go other players in the educational scene, namely teachers.

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